

Case Study

Employment Productivity Strategy at Vocational High School: Case Study Darur Roja West Java Indonesia

Ahmad Azmy¹

Graduate School, Paramadina University, Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract

This study describes an employee productivity model that has been implemented in the Darur Roja Vocational School. The approach used is descriptive qualitative and case studies. The process of collecting data through observation and interviews in making employee productivity models. Recruitment & selection of employees is the initial process in obtaining human resources according to organizational needs. Training & development is an effort to fulfill employee competence according to educational demands. Employee productivity must always be strived to be able to compete with competitors to be able to achieve organizational expectations. The family culture is unique for vocational schools so that employee productivity can always be increased according to organizational achievements.

Keywords: Employee Productivity, Recruitment & Selection, Training & Development, Organizational Culture

Introduction

Resources are anything that is a company asset to achieve their goals. Resources owned by the company can be categorized into four types of resources, such as financial, physical, human, and technological capabilities. Financial resources are one of the important elements to form a company that is advanced and on a global scale. Physical resources are resources related to physically supporting the establishment of a company such as technology, machinery, and other fittings. Human resources are a central and important sector to achieve goals in a company, because with the ability of workers' skills and quality of human resources to move the company properly and correctly.

¹ Corresponding author's email: azmy33@gmail.com

Technological capability is also an important supporting element in moving the company because the complete technology and technological sophistication will facilitate the running of a company. Of the four sources, the most important aspect is humans, because humans are the most important mover in a company. Whether the company is progressing or not depends on the management of human resources, it can be done within a company or by a particular department. Human resources have different characteristics from other resources so that they require planning and development of employee productivity. This component has a unique characteristic, namely human nature that varies from one another, has a mindset that is not inanimate objects. Humans need to be treated as whole humans in various ways so that each individual can carry out the work, rules, and orders that exist in the organization to get maximum performance.

Productivity is what all organizations want to increase business scale through human resources. An organization, both large and small, will be moved by the importance of improving the level of work productivity (Sedarmayanti, 2016). Productivity can be influenced by leadership style, motivation, the external environment of the organization, and the level of education (Kamuli, 2012). Productivity will affect discipline, motivation, and morale (Dotulong & Assagaf, 2015). Organizations must be able to pay attention to internal and external factors of employees that affect individual and organizational performance (Kehoe & Wright, 2013). Productivity will make work experience valuable for employees by paying attention to wages and other external factors (HOLZER, 1990).

Designing employee productivity must be in line with the organizational strategy. Strategies are compiled and implemented to achieve various organizational goals. Organizational effectiveness will be in line with how the ability to formulate activities and execute strategies properly (Miles et al., 2013). Strategic planning is prepared to be able to execute business goals and achieve final targets so that differentiation makes the organization more competitive than competitors. The combination of the core strategy is differentiation, quality management, and organizational performance (Prajogo & Sohal, 2006). Organizations must be able to compete globally so that they need reliable and wide-ranging human resources (Ismail, 2016). A well-planned and long-term oriented strategy will provide a differentiating position for organizations in the business market (Kumar et al., 2011). Therefore, organizations must be able to pay attention to organizational structure, culture, external and internal barriers in strategy execution (Alshammari, 2015).

Based on the explanation above, this study will analyze how an organization increases employee productivity. A case study was taken at a vocational school in West Java on how to increase the productivity of human resources in providing performance for the quality of education. Productivity will be able to provide an overview of organizational processes and employee performance. The taking of vocational schools as research objects is due to their uniqueness in approaching employees so that they can increase the productivity of human resources.

Literature Review

Employee Productivity

Productivity includes a mental attitude that always has the view that today's life must be better than yesterday. The way of working today must be better, and the results of tomorrow must be greater. The productivity of the bag is a measure of the quantity and quality of work that has been done, taking into account the cost of the resources used to do the work (Mathis & Jackson, 2006). Work productivity will be able to increase systematic accountability in assessing and steaming employee performance (Hubertus, 2016). Factors that must be considered in productivity are training, physical work environment, and employee motivation (Lestari & Sriathi, 2013). The motivational factor is very important in how an organization can maintain productivity in the long term (Hayati Nasution & Musnadi, 2018)

Organizations must create information and knowledge management systems for employee productivity (Liengme et al., 2015). Work productivity must pay attention to the relationship between superiors and subordinates in an organizational structure (Manik & Syafrina, 2018). The skill level is determined by the level of formal and informal education, the consistency of training programs, and skills that will affect employee productivity (Nasron & Astuti, 2016). Employee productivity can be assessed by the use of material inputs, labor, business capital, and the availability of information resources (Priscilia, 2017). Work productivity will be able to have implications for the design of strategies, competencies, facilities, motivation, and work experience (Syarif et al., 2014). Efforts to maintain employee productivity by providing competitive compensation, bonuses, and promotion (Rahmawati, 2013). Therefore, employee productivity must be considered by the organization in achieving its overall business goals and targets.

Employee Recruitment

Employee productivity can be started with employee recruitment according to the company's business needs. The recruitment process begins with receiving an application letter as a prerequisite for job qualification and the continuity of the process through selection for all company positions (Kurnia & Santoso, 2018). The effectiveness of recruitment and selection can affect the increase in employee productivity and performance (Azmy, 2019; Kartodikromo et al., 2017; Yullyanti, 2009a). The recruitment process will find the right candidate in carrying out the job process appropriately and efficiently. Employee selection will be carried out to measure the candidate's ability to meet job qualifications and positions offered by the organization (Adu-darkoh, 2014; Campbell, 2012; Cortina & Luchman, 2012). Recruitment constraints encountered are internal processes, absence of candidates in the labor market, and organizational external factors (Setiani, 2013). The effectiveness of recruitment and selection will have a direct effect on employee performance (Yullyanti, 2009b). Employee selection is the process of selecting the best candidates to fill company positions (Dessler, 2017; Hasibuan, S.P, 2014; Noe et al., 2009). Therefore, recruitment and selection are needed to maintain employee productivity related to individual and organizational performance.

Organizational Strategy

Strategic planning is planning to achieve organizational goals using existing resources (Rusniati & Haq, 2014). Strategic planning is very important in organizations because this strategic planning applies to the organization as a whole (Ismail, 2016). The focus of

the organization must be to produce and master science with a strong religiosity base in achieving organizational planning (Joyce, 2015). Organizational effectiveness, organizational effectiveness is a construct of organizational success, where this construct can be broken down into various dimensions or variables that affect the achievement of business targets (Ettlie et al., 1984). Therefore, the organizational strategy is very important in maintaining focus and achieving the company's business targets.

The effectiveness of educational organizations in strategy is conducting environmental scanning, formulating teaching plans, implementing activities, executing targets, and evaluating employees in achieving job targets (Amin, 2016). Planning is needed to determine what goals and activities must be carried out to achieve organizational expectations (Daft, 2007). A strategy is an organizational master plan that explains how the company will achieve all its goals based on its long-term vision and mission (Rangkuti, 2013). Strategic plans are needed in maintaining the running of the organization and mapping the activities carried out by employees. Productivity and performance are needed by organizations so that they can create a conducive work environment (Alshammari, 2015).

Research Methodology

This study uses a qualitative approach and descriptive-based case studies. The process of collecting data by conducting a literature study, observation, and interviews. The interview process is a dyad (interpersonal) communication process, with predetermined goals are seriously designed to create interactions that involve asking and answering questions (Ryan et al., 2009). The interview process will lead to a discussion of certain problems accompanied by the interaction of questions with answers both physically and non-physically (Qu & Dumay, 2011). The interaction process of the two parties is used to explore information needs that are relevant to an issue or topic discussion so that it can reach a comprehensive conclusion (Turner, 2010).

Data were collected through open interviews between the researcher and the Head of the Vocational High School (SMK) Darur Roja. Researchers have prepared several questions that will be asked of the Principal of Vocational High School (SMK) Darur Roja. Data collection is done by extracting information from one of the vocational schools that has a top and strategic position in the organizational structure. The principal is the highest position for managing employees, developing competencies, delegating work, supervising the teaching process, and comprehensively evaluating performance.

Results & Discussion

Based on the results of interviews and observations, we found that the implementation of employee productivity in vocational schools begins with the recruitment process for teachers and employees. The recruitment process by looking at educational standards, competency requirements, and work experience. Respondents explained that teacher productivity will show how the recruitment process is carried out effectively and according to teaching needs. The selection process was carried out simply, namely teaching practice and interviews. Teachers who are accepted will be given a trial process for 1 year and evaluation is carried out periodically according to the end of the contract.

The effectiveness of recruitment will greatly show employee productivity according to organizational expectations (Li, 2015; Omisore & Okofu, 2014). The correct recruitment process will adjust the job design according to the needs of the organization (Mangaleswaran & Kirushanthan, 2015).

Respondents explained that every year the school always sends its employees to take part in training both carried out by the government and private sector. The results of the interview explained that an organization that can carry out the effectiveness of recruitment, employee selection, and job training will be able to increase employee productivity (Hanaysha, 2016; Sutanto & Kurniawan, 2016). This vocational school has conducted recruitment through a process of interviews, teaching tests, and written tests to measure the ability of prospective teachers and employees. This result has been proven by increasing student satisfaction with the quality of teaching.

The results of the interview explained the lack of resources in the employee recruitment process. Respondents explained that the obstacles faced were internal and external factors. Internal factors include a lack of human resources and facilities. External factors include network deficiencies and the inability to manage the organization efficiently. This is normal for a small organization that is still developing through experience, habits, and continuous evaluation (Guangjin, 2012; Sinha, 2014). Researchers assess that the recruitment process is still not optimal due to a lack of information that schools are looking for new teacher candidates. Lack of information related to job vacancies and there are still people who do not know the name of the school by the community so that it requires increased branding according to organizational needs.

Darur Roja vocational school uses social media such as YouTube, Facebook, and Instagram to introduce school programs, teacher profiles, and alumni quality. Job vacancies are posted through the website and social media to facilitate access for job applicants. Promotion through social media is very effective in increasing wider access to the community (Castronovo & Huang, 2012; Malthouse et al., 2013). This greatly makes it easier for prospective parents to get to know school profiles, educational programs, and learning standards. Several studies have shown that social media is very effective in promoting products, both goods and services (Duffett, 2017; Paquette, 2013; Schivinski & Dabrowski, 2016).

Respondents explained that the strategy used in improving employee productivity is to instill an organizational culture in depth by the organization's values. Darur Roja Vocational School always strives to instill strong Islamism values. The values of the organization are to print a smart and sincere generation of karimah, amaliyah knowledge, and high-quality human resources. Focus on teaching and competency preparation by conducting teacher and employee skills improvement programs. The discipline and example of employees are important in providing a good example for all students. Teachers who always enter on time will provide guarantees of academic quality. An obligation for vocational schools to have the consistent implementation of organizational culture and aims to maintain the productivity of human resources (Ramly & Syukur, 2018; Susanto, 2012).

The Principal of Vocational School, Darur Roja, has carried out good organizational management. The approach is taken by increasing employee participation in the decision-making process. School leaders try to provide an example for all employees and teachers. Every morning briefing employees and teachers. The briefing process aims to remind the obligations of teachers and employees. Both of these functions are vital for maintaining academic quality. Teachers must produce learning innovations and competencies for the student learning process. Employees must provide the best service to students. Therefore, all work must be done professionally and maintain the trust of parents.

These results are in line with several studies which explain that the effectiveness of organizational strategy must have the ability to scan the environment, formulate strategies, and evaluate employee performance (Angle & Perry, 1981; Balser & McClusky, 2005; Golman & Bhatia, 2012; Sundaray, 2011). The implementation of the strategy that has been carried out includes scanning the school environment. The way this is done is that school leaders go directly to the field and review the state of the teaching interaction process. The performance evaluation process is by holding regular meetings at least 4 times a month so that they can respond quickly if any work problems are found related to teaching and student services. Supervision is always carried out consistently to maintain the quality of student learning according to government regulations.

The conductivity of the work environment greatly determines employee productivity (Mashudi, 2016). According to the results of interviews with respondents, vocational schools always design a comfortable and safe work environment for all employees. Vocational school foundation leaders always hold workshops and pieces of training for all employees. Training programs are designed according to teacher needs or following technical guidance recommended by the government. This is very useful to improve the abilities and competencies of all employees of the Darur Roja vocational school. Several research results prove that the success of training programs can increase employee productivity (Chen, 2014; Jehanzeb & Ahmed Bashir, 2013). Darur Roja vocational school has been very good in providing training programs for teachers and employees.

Organizational culture will shape the work patterns to be carried out by employees. Respondents explained that the family culture is very close at Darur Roja Vocational School. This is very influential in employee productivity in carrying out tasks according to job descriptions. The school considers that employees and teachers are the long-term assets of the organization. Starting from the top level to the bottom of applying effective communication patterns. This is done to anticipate misinformation and reduce the risk of problems between employees and superiors.

Respondents explained that maintaining the relationship between superiors and employees is one of the priorities for maintaining work productivity. Darur Roja vocational school ensures that in the process of work, school leaders always explain work programs and understand the school curriculum. School leaders must ensure the work conductivity of employees and foster a sense of comfort in the school environment. This is confirmed from several research results that the relationship between superiors and employees must be maintained in achieving work quality (Ling Suan & Mohd Nasurdin, 2016; Wang et al., 2019). According to the results of interviews with respondents, both of these have been implemented optimally so that employee productivity can be

maintained during the teaching year. Besides the organization always provides rewards for employees who excel through bonuses or prizes at the end of each year. The Family Gathering program is always held to strengthen good relations between employees and school leaders. Organizations realize that employee productivity can be increased through strong and solid teamwork.

A job promotion system is used to increase employee productivity. Darur Roja vocational school provides promotions for employees who can provide the best performance both in terms of the work process and planning aspects. This is done to always increase employee motivation. The results of the study explain that work motivation will have positive implications for employee productivity (Iskandar et al., 2009). The promotion process that has been carried out by Darur Roja is carried out through achievements and work experience while being an employee or teacher. Then the measurement process is carried out according to the student's assessment at the end of each semester. Achievements and work experience must be used as the basis for granting promotions to employees (Medhiantari & Yuniari, 2016).

Discipline is one of the essential components of employee productivity (Dunggio, 2013). An explanation from the respondent that the Darur Roja vocational school always monitors the attendance of employees and teachers. The attendance process uses a manual book and fingerprint system. The employee absentee level is only given a maximum of 1 month and should not exceed a day off. If the employee absentee exceeds the school requirements, a penalty will be given in the form of a Level I Warning Letter according to the procedure set by the Foundation. For employees who do not have attendance for 1 semester, the school will provide a salary bonus as a form of employee appreciation.

Recommendation

Based on the results of research through interviews and observations with the Darur Roja vocational school, we found the employee productivity strategy model in vocational schools as shown in Figure 1. The model explains that in implementing employee productivity strategies in vocational schools is to ensure the effectiveness of communication. An effective communication process can be done through meetings both online and offline. Various applications can be used such as Zoom, Google Meet, or other applications to implement remote meetings. The effectiveness of communication can ensure employee understanding to achieve job targets and maximum contribution by the teacher. A comfortable work environment is needed for employees from a psychological and physical aspect. The provision of a work environment must be considered by schools so that they can achieve what is expected from the contribution of employees.

A good relationship between employees and leaders can create strong solid teamwork. The support of leaders and employees is the key to organizational success in achieving job targets. The application of a reward and punishment system must be carried out consistently. This system functions to select employees who have the best performance and are given career development opportunities. This must be supported by employee discipline. The attendance system that has been implemented optimally by the school. Dimensions must be the concern of the organization to maintain employee productivity. A competitive promotion system must be implemented consistently. The promotion will

be able to increase employees' expectations for a long-term career. The application of organizational culture in a friendly manner can increase employee productivity. This culture will be able to carry out the work process comprehensively. The feeling of helping and helping each other is so close that they are ready to replace if one is unable to complete the job.

Figure I. Employee Productivity Model Vocational School

The two things that add to the employee productivity model are influenced by employee recruitment & selection and consistent training & development. Recruitment and selection of employees is the first thing that must be carried out by the organization. Human resource needs must be met through an effective recruitment and selection process. The school must always strive to improve the competency process through workshops, technical guidance, and short courses. Training & development must be carried out consistently to answer the challenges and expectations of parents of students who leave their children to be printed as competitive human resources.

Conclusion

The results of the conclusions of this study are as follows:

1. The employee productivity strategy is supported by five factors consisting of communication effectiveness, comfortable work environment, superior-good relationship & subordinates, punishment & reward system based on employee contribution, high employee discipline, competitive job promotion system, and family organizational culture.

2. These seven dimensions have been implemented well by the Darur Roja Vocational School to always increase employee productivity both in the short and long term.

3. Research can be continued using evaluation research models, quantitative regression, and other qualitative ones that can be adjusted to the scale of the organization.

4. Recruitment & selection and training & development are the main processes in employee productivity. These two things are to ensure the need for human resources and competence according to the demands of the school. These two dimensions can be used as intervening variables in the research model.

5. Five factors in the employee productivity model can be used as dimensions with indicators tailored to the needs of the study.

6. This study suggests using a quantitative approach by analyzing the relationship between independent and dependent variables. This aims to map which variables have the highest implications in employee productivity models, especially in vocational schools.

References

- Adu-darkoh, M. (2014). Employee Recruitment and Selection Practices in the. *Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology In*. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JB.185.11.3307>
- Alshammari, H. (2015). Workplace Productivity through Employee Workforce Engagement: A Review Study. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*.
- Amin, M. (2016). Impelemntasi Manajemen Strategis Kepala Sekolah Menengah

Pertama Kabupaten Serang. <https://Media.Neliti.Com/Media/Publications/256442-Impelemntasi-Manajemen-Strategis-Kepala-F2b09c83.Pdf>.

- Angle, H. L., & Perry, J. L. (1981). An Empirical Assessment of Organizational Commitment and Organizational Effectiveness. *Administrative Science Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2392596>
- Azmy, A. (2019). Evaluation of Lecturer Recruitment Program at Tanri Abeng University. *International Journal of Management, Accounting, & Economics*, 6(7). http://www.ijmae.com/files/accepted/1009_final.pdf
- Balser, D., & McClusky, J. (2005). Managing stakeholder relationships and nonprofit organization effectiveness. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.70>
- Campbell, D. (2012). Employee Selection as a Control System. *Journal of Accounting Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-679X.2012.00457.x>
- Castronovo, C., & Huang, L. (2012). Social Media in an Alternative Marketing Communication Model. *Journal of Marketing Development and Competitiveness*.
- Chen, M. (2014). *The Effect of Training on Employee Retention*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/gecss-14.2014.90>
- Cortina, J. M., & Luchman, J. N. (2012). Personnel Selection and Employee Performance. In *Handbook of Psychology, Second Edition*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118133880.hop212007>
- Daft, R. L. (2007). Organization theory and design. In *Organization Theory and Design*.
- Dessler, G. (2017). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. In *Pelatihan dan Pengembangan*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2505515.2507827>
- Dotulong, L., & Assagaf, S. (2015). Pengaruh Disiplin, Motivasi Dan Semangat Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Pegawai Dinas Pendapatan Daerah Kota Manado. *Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis Dan Akuntansi*.
- Duffett, R. G. (2017). Influence of social media marketing communications on young consumers' attitudes. *Young Consumers*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/YC-07-2016-00622>
- Dunggio, M. (2013). Semangat Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Pada Pt. Jasa Raharja (Persero) Cabang Sulawesi Utara. *Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis Dan Akuntansi*.
- Ettlie, J. E., Bridges, W. P., & O'Keefe, R. D. (1984). Organization Strategy And Structural Differences For Radical Versus Incremental Innovation. *Management of Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.30.6.682>

- Golman, R., & Bhatia, S. (2012). Performance evaluation inflation and compression. *Accounting, Organizations, and Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aos.2012.09.001>
- Guangjin, C. (2012). Organizational structure. In *Social Structure of Contemporary China*. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jsm.1.1.74>
- Hanaysha, J. (2016). Testing the Effects of Employee Engagement, Work Environment, and Organizational Learning on Organizational Commitment. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.07.139>
- Hasibuan, S.P, M. (2014). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. In *Bumi Aksara Jakarta*.
- Hayati Nasution, E., & Musnadi. (2018). Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Kepuasan Kerja Dan Dampaknya Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Kanwil Direktorat Jenderal Kekayaan Negara Aceh. *Bisnis Unsyiah*, 2(1), 2018–2123.
- HOLZER, H. J. (1990). The Determinants of Employee Productivity and Earnings. *Industrial Relations: A Journal of Economy and Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-232X.1990.tb00761.x>
- Hubertus, O. (2016). Penerapan Manajemen Strategi Dalam Mewujudkan Kinerja Organisasi Sektor Publik. *Societas: Ilmu Administrasi Dan Sosial*.
- Iskandar, R., Melaniawati, & Sukarno, A. (2009). Pengaruh Motivasi Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan. *UG Journal*.
- Ismail, D. H. (2016). Strategi Mewujudkan Suatu Organisasi Pembelajar. *Lentera Bisnis*.
- Jehanzeb, K., & Ahmed Bashir, N. (2013). Training and Development Program and its Benefits to Employee and Organization: A Conceptual Study. *European Journal of Business and Management*.
- Joyce, P. (2015). Strategic Management in the Public Sector. In *Strategic Management in the Public Sector*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315740355>
- Kamuli, S. (2012). Pengaruh Iklim Organisasi Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Pegawai di Sekretariat Daerah Kota Gorontalo. *Jurnal Inovasi*.
- Kartodikromo, E., Tewal, B., & Trang, I. (2017). Proses Rekrutmen, Seleksi, Pelatihan Kerja Dan Pengaruhnya Pada Kinerja Karyawan Cv. Celebes Indonesia Sakti Mer 99 Mega Mas Manado. *Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis Dan Akuntansi*. <https://doi.org/10.35794/emba.v5i2.15625>
- Kehoe, R. R., & Wright, P. M. (2013). The Impact of High-Performance Human Resource Practices on Employees' Attitudes and Behaviors. *Journal of Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206310365901>
- Kumar, K., Subramanian, R., & Strandholm, K. (2011). Market Orientation And Performance: Does Organizational Strategy Matter? *Journal of Applied Business*

- Research (JABR)*. <https://doi.org/10.19030/jabr.v18i1.2099>
- Kurnia, R. M., & Santoso, M. B. (2018). Proses Rekrutmen Dan Seleksi Pekerja K31 Unpad. *Focus : Jurnal Pekerjaan Sosial*. <https://doi.org/10.24198/focus.v1i2.18264>
- Lestari, P., & Sriathi, A. (2013). Pengaruh Pelatihan Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja Fisik Serta Motivasi Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Pegawai Pada Pt. Taspen (Persero) Kantor Cabang Denpasar. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana*.
- Li, T. (2015). Nestle Employee Recruitment Research. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 6(41), 97–113.
- Liengme, B. V., Stolojan, V., Banks, M., Mierke, C. T., Başkal, S., Kim, Y. S., Noz, M. E., Tyson, R. K., Geometry, R., Analysis, G., Rodgers, P., Palmer, S., Palmer, K., Wood, M. A., Simoen, E., Claeys, C., Sperrin, M., Riedel, M. F., ... Seifert, F. (2015). Analisis Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Outsourcing Pada Pt Siantar Putra Mandiri. *Metrologia*. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s1809-98232013000400007>
- Ling Suan, C., & Mohd Nasurdin, A. (2016). Supervisor support and work engagement of hotel employees in Malaysia: Is it different for men and women? *Gender in Management*, 31(1), 2–18. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GM-11-2014-0105>
- Malthouse, E. C., Haenlein, M., Skiera, B., Wege, E., & Zhang, M. (2013). Managing customer relationships in the social media era: Introducing the social CRM house. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2013.09.008>
- Mangaleswaran, T., & Kirushanthan, K. (2015). Job description and job specification: A study of selected organizations in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Information Technology and Business Management*, 41(1), 30–36. www.jitbm.com
- Manik, S., & Syafrina, N. (2018). Faktor-faktor yang mempengaruhi produktivitas kerja karyawan pada bank danamon simpan pinjam. *Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Islam (Maqdis)*.
- Mashudi, M. (2016). Pengaruh Stressor Di Tempat Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Akademik Tenaga Pengajar (Dosen) Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo. *Ekuitas (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan)*. <https://doi.org/10.24034/j25485024.y2003.v7.i2.1977>
- Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. H. (2006). Changing Nature of Human Resource Management. *Human Resource Management*.
- Medhiantari, I. A. N., & Yuniari, M. (2016). Pengaruh Prestasi Kerja Dan Pengalaman Kerja Terhadap Promosi Jabatan Pada PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Cabang Gajah Mada Denpasar. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Unud*.
- Miles, R. E., Snow, C. C., Meyer, A. D., & Coleman, H. J. (2013). Organizational Strategy, Structure, *Management*.

- Nasron, & Astuti, T. B. (2016). Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Produktivitas Kerja (Studi Pada Karyawan Bagian Produksi PT Mazuvo Indo). *Jurnal Kajian Akuntansi Dan Bisnis*.
- Noe, R. A., Hollenbeck, J. R., Gerhart, B., & Wright, P. M. (2009). Fundamentals of Human Resource Management. In *Boston: McGraw-Hill*. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PRS.0b013e31822214c1>
- Omisore, B. O., & Okofu, B. I. (2014). Staff Recruitment and Selection Process in the Nigerian Public Service: What is to be done? *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 4(3), 280. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijhrs.v4i3.6367>
- Paquette, H. (2013). Social Media as a Marketing Tool: A Literature Review. *Major Papers by Master of Science Students*.
- Prajogo, D. I., & Sohal, A. S. (2006). The relationship between organization strategy, total quality management (TQM), and organization performance - The mediating role of TQM. *European Journal of Operational Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2004.03.033>
- Priscilia, P. (2017). Analisis Produktivitas Kerja Pada PT. Berkat Anugerah Raya. *Agora*.
- Qu, S. Q., & Dumay, J. (2011). The qualitative research interview. In *Qualitative Research in Accounting and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/11766091111162070>
- Rahmawati, desi. (2013). Pengaruh Motivasi Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Pr Fajar Berlian Tulungagung. *Jurnal Universitas Tulungagung Bonorowo*.
- Ramly, A. T., & Syukur, D. A. (2018). Strategic Management of Organization Development and Civil Service Based PumpingHR Model at Ibn Khaldun University Bogor. *Integrated Journal of Business and Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.33019/ijbe.v2i1.59>
- Rangkuti, F. (2013). Teknik Membedah Kasus Bisnis Analisis SWOT Cara Perhitungan Bobot, Rating, dan OCAI. In *PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama. Jakarta*.
- Rusniati, & Haq, A. (2014). Perencanaan Strategis dalam Perspektif Organisasi. *Intekna*, 2(2), 102–209. [http://download.portalgaruda.org/article.php?article=352623&val=8097&title=perencanaan strategis dalam perspektif organisasi](http://download.portalgaruda.org/article.php?article=352623&val=8097&title=perencanaan%20strategis%20dalam%20perspektif%20organisasi)
- Ryan, F., Coughlan, M., & Cronin, P. (2009). Interviewing in qualitative research: The one-to-one interview. *International Journal of Therapy and Rehabilitation*. <https://doi.org/10.12968/ijtr.2009.16.6.42433>
- Schivinski, B., & Dabrowski, D. (2016). The effect of social media communication on consumer perceptions of brands. *Journal of Marketing Communications*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527266.2013.871323>

- Sedarmayanti. (2016). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. In *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*.
- Setiani, B. (2013). Kajian Sumber Daya Manusia Dalam Proses Rekrutmen Tenaga Kerja Di Perusahaan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Widya*, 1(1), 38–44. <http://e-journal.jurwidyakop3.com/index.php/jurnal-ilmiah/article/view/106>
- Sinha, J. (2014). Organizational Behaviour. In *Culture and Organizational Behaviour*. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9788132100997.n1>
- Sundaray, B. K. (2011). Employee Engagement: A Driver of Organizational Effectiveness. *European Journal of Business and Management*.
- Susanto, H. (2012). Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Kinerja Guru The Factors Of Affecting The Performance Of The Teachers ' Of State Vocational High School. *Jurnal Pendidikan Vokasi*.
- Sutanto, E. M., & Kurniawan, M. (2016). The impact of recruitment, employee retention and labor relations to employee performance on batik industry in Solo city, Indonesia. *International Journal of Business and Society*. <https://doi.org/10.33736/ijbs.531.2016>
- Syarif, A. A., Sinulingga, S., & Nazaruddin, N. (2014). Penentuan Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Produktivitas Tenaga Kerja Di Pt. Intan Suar Kartika Dan Rancangan Strategi Perbaikan. *Teknovasi*.
- Turner, D. W. (2010). Qualitative interview design: A practical guide for novice investigators. *Qualitative Report*.
- Wang, M., Guo, T., Ni, Y., Shang, S., & Tang, Z. (2019). The effect of spiritual leadership on employee effectiveness: An intrinsic motivation perspective. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02627>
- Yullyanti, E. (2009a). Analisis Proses Rekrutmen dan Seleksi pada Kinerja Pegawai. *Analisis Proses Rekrutmen Dan Seleksi Pada Kinerja Pegawai*, 16(1996), 131–139.
- Yullyanti, E. (2009b). Analisis Proses Rekrutmen dan Seleksi pada Kinerja Pegawai. *Analisis Proses Rekrutmen Dan Seleksi Pada Kinerja Pegawai*.

COPYRIGHTS

©2020 The author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.

HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE

Azmy, A. (2020). Employment Productivity Strategy at Vocational High School: Case Study Darur Roja West Java Indonesia. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics*, 7(11), 660-674.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4342563

URL: http://www.ijmae.com/article_120555.html

